

Animation and Visual Effects: An implication to Adult Learning and Civic roles in Democracy

Author Details: Muhammad Alkali PhD.

Department of Adult Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto Nigeria.

Abstract

Adult education is essential to democracy and development, and adult education can be tool for bridging about political, social, cultural and economic development of Nigeria. By these it is important to alien adult learning to a strategy and process that learning is made fun, interesting, and easier and to also connect it to democracy that can enable human and national growths. Animation attracts and capture attention because motion is one of the primaries attributes of a graphic that makes viewers take notice. Animations can also increase motivation because of their novelty, visual effects attract attention which can be used to democratize politics; the adult learners who are the voters require literacy to communicate and voter literacy to enable all to participate in deciding who to govern them. ICT inform of visual effect is used by citizens and civil society for networking and enhances advocacy and mobilization, locally and globally more particularly using animations and visual effects. whatapps, Facebook and posters create new modes of social interaction. The use of animation through mobile phones can facilitate the modelling of election processes and the use of SMS for networking and mobilization. In government, ICT may increase accountability and transparency, and counter corruption through more efficient administration and increased flows of information.

Keywords: Animation, Visual effects, Adult learning

Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) is a term that refers to a variety of technologies that facilitate communications and information sharing. Most often they are computer-mediated forms such as the Internet, including email and the World Wide Web also including mobile phone use and games. Despite the ubiquity of these ICTs in all facets of our life, there has been amazingly little written in our informal and critical adult education literature. We see far more in the distance education literature which tends to focus on the technical aspects of these ICTs and their use in formal education environments. Yet, it is clear to those of us in the informal and non-formal sphere that the use of ICTs to mobilize, educate and communicate is at record proportions.

A study conducted by Viviana (2015) on use of ICT in Adult learning has found that participants perceive the integration of ICTs into the adult education program as innovative tools that positively enhance their teaching and learning processes. Consequently, this study reveals that both program's teachers and students view the use of ICTs in and outside the classroom as an innovation that promote interactive and dynamic classes. In addition, findings suggest that participants' perceptions of the integration and use of ICTs in the education program closely relates to their motivations to teach, study and learn. Also, participants' perceive the integration of ICTs into the education program and their communities as an opportunity to access knowledge and information as well as to communicate with others and thereof enter the digital world. Despite findings generally show that participants views are largely positive, there are also other conflicting aspects that reveal participants' negative perceptions. For instance, the ICT tools integrated in the program are considered as very difficult devices to handle by some of the participants, which considerably limit the use of these tools for their teaching and learning process. Animation; Animation is a method in which pictures are manipulated to appear as moving images. Animation and Visual Effects are a way of mixing real film shooting with false or animated images. For instance, a movie that shows the hero jumping off the ground and flying into the air, is created using VFX. almost every single movie these days uses VFX. Animation attracts and capture attention because motion is one of the primary attributes of a graphic that makes viewers take notice.

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Use Animations for Adult Learning

Moving pictures are hard to resist. But research shows when compared to static graphics, animations get mixed reviews as an effective learning medium. Fortunately, there are ways to make animations more effective. Types of Animation for Learning

There are many types of animation that can be used for instructional purposes, including:

- 2-D animation: Creating the illusion of motion by the rapid display of a sequence of static images or frames that minimally differ from one another.
- 3-D animation: Creating the illusion of moving objects rendered from 3-D wireframes. Based on mathematical algorithms, the objects can be rotated and moved over time.
- Motion graphics: Moving graphical elements and text across the screen. This is what we create with certain authoring and presentation tools.
- Transformations: Animations that depict changes without movement, such as color transformations (a person blushing) or lines changing from thin to thick (clogged arteries maybe?).
- Stop-motion animation: Photographs of an object shown in a quick sequence to create the illusion of movement.

Affective Purpose

Animations attract and capture attention because motion is one of the primary attributes of a graphic that makes viewers take notice. Animations can also increase motivation because of their novelty. When they are humorous, they can create a positive effect. One newer approach is the animated information graphic (see an example from the Articulate community), which can be used for introductory explanations that may seem boring otherwise.

Cognitive Purpose

Animations that have a cognitive purpose can facilitate learning because they provide more and different information than static graphics. They have the potential to help a learner build a more accurate mental model of a system's behavior compared to graphics alone (Schnotz and Rasch, 2005). There are many functions that animation can fulfill, such as:

- explaining a dynamic process
- visualizing things what cannot be seen with the naked eye
- simulating a system
- making abstract concepts more concrete (such as with visual metaphors)

- visualizing quantitative data
- improving one’s spatial abilities
- depicting hosts and agents that explain
- telling a story
- creating a learning game or elements in a game
- constructing knowledge in mathematics.

Animation and Civic roles in Democracy

Moving pictures are hard to resist. but research shows when compared to static graphics, animations get mixed reviews as an effective learning medium. fortunately, there are ways to make animations more effective. All efforts in the electoral process will amount to zero if the electorates fail to turn out to cast their votes on election days. To this end, the extent to which the media either through posters, succeed in mobilizing the citizens to participate in the electoral process will largely determine the depth and strength of democracy in the land. People must be mobilized such that they are able to make informed political decisions

Voting; is the means by which such expression is made, as a ballot or ticket. an indication of choice, opinion, or will on a question, such as the choosing of a candidate, by or as if by some recognized means, such as a ballot paper or card

Voting is an express opinion of group of persons as determined by voting it was put to the vote; do not take a vote; it came to a vote. In Nigeria today voting have the following steps and process; this animations are examples on how it can use, cartoons and pictures have in local content including mode dress and the environments

Step 1

Step 2

Step 3

ACCREDITATION PROCESS

1. Take your registration card to the venue you registered and join a queue.

2. Show your voters card to the electoral official who will check for your details.

3. The electoral official will mark your finger signifying that you are cleared to vote in that polling unit.

Step 4

VOTING PROCESS

1. The electoral official will explain the voting process to the accredited voters.

2. Join the voting queue.

3. The electoral official marks your finger and gives a ballot paper on which you will cast your vote.

Step 5

VOTING PROCESS

4. Enter the polling unit boot to cast your vote by thumb printing next to the logo of your desired candidate.

5. Drop your ballot slip into the ballot box.

By completing this process, you have successfully voted

Example of voting in Nigeria

Guideline for using Animation in an Adult Education programs

Is a motion graphic video really the most effective way to motivate learners? Is the investment of time and resources to produce an animated video ultimately worth it? The short answer is, we don't know. Studies comparing static graphics vs. animations in eLearning have shown mixed results. However, there is strong evidence to support several best practices for using animation for training.

Best Practices for Using Motion Graphics and Animation For Training

1. Keep It Simple

One danger of using animations is overloading your audience with fast-paced, highly visual, content-dense material. There's only so much information the human brain can process at a time. Using images with reduced realism (for example, trading stock photography for illustrations, or switching a complex diagram to a simplified line drawn version) will help learners more easily comprehend and retain training content.

2. Give Learners the Option To Replay

One of the greatest strengths of web-based training is its ability to let learners personalize and self-pace their learning experiences. You can optimize this strength by chunking animations into short, focused training on a specific topic, then providing an option for learners to replay animations as many times as needed. Not only will learners use this feature to ensure they understand the material in their initial training experience, it's likely that learners will be more inclined to revisit the training material for future performance support or quick training refreshers.

3. Pair It with the Right Content

Animation really shines when it's used to demonstrate complex processes, reveal things not visible with the naked eye, or make information more memorable. Let's imagine that you're building employee onboarding for a company that sells high speed internet. If you needed to show your learners how the internet delivers digital content instantly to millions of devices across the globe, an illustrated animation could be a perfect solution. However, if you needed to show a new internet sales employee how to conduct a meeting with a client, you'd be much better served with live video, audio, or even text-based scripts that model best practices. Learn more about when to use live video vs animation here.

4. Use Audio to Maximize Working Memory

While it's true that all humans have a limited capacity for ingesting new information, animation maximizes this capacity by delivering information in two ways: Auditory and visual. This two-channel delivery system boosts the amount of

content learners can encounter before reaching maximum load for working memory. While it's important to not abuse this advantage (see tip #1), it is possible to achieve greater results with less seat-time using animation.

3 Common Mistakes in Using Animations and Motion Graphics and How to Avoid Them

In addition to following best practices, beware of these common mistakes Instructional Designers frequently commit when using animations and motion graphics in eLearning courses.

1. Too Much Text

Heavy use of text on the screen in animations or motion graphics can distract learners from the main concept. Worse still is when verbatim text appears on the screen while a narrator reads the text aloud. Avoid splitting the attention of the learner by using audio narration and only showing text on the screen to highlight key points. For learners who prefer or require it, a transcript or closed captioning can be a secondary option.

2. Unfocused Priorities

Animations, by nature, have a lot of moving parts. Added characters, background music, complex movements and transitions all help make the content engaging. However, with so much going on, learners might miss the main point, or struggle to identify key concepts. Use visual cues to highlight the primary objective of the animation and help learners prioritize what to remember.

3. Ignoring Your Audience

With the many tools and resources available to create animations and motion graphics, it can be easy to get carried away. While a cartoon puppy or curlicue font might be a temptation when you're storyboarding your motion graphic, consider the unique characteristics of your audience and what style or voice would best engage them in the experience. What would feel most authentic to them? What stories, characters, humor, or voice would best match the environment and attitude of your learners? While it's okay to be creative, going too far in a direction that feels immature or inauthentic to your audience will drastically impact the effectiveness of your animation.

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